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Malayo Pa, Pero Malapit Na: The Perks, Fights, and Social Realities of a Third-Year Educ Students

There is a certain kind of quiet transformation that happens when you reach your third year in university. Realizations, expectations, doubt, and judgment surround it. It is the time when you will experience sleepless nights, overload requirements, and unfinished activities. Then, you will realize that you are no longer the same student who once asked, "Kaya ko kaya?"

Now, the question feels different. It's no longer about if you can; instead, it's about how you will survive.

This is what the third year feels like. Hindi na dapat freshman na nangangapa pa lang. Sabi nga nila, "Third year ka na, dapat alam mo na yan". This message adds pressure. People expect you to know better, do better, be better. It will remind you that you need to improve and upgrade your level because the subjects are no longer introductory; you need to think critically, provide an in-depth understanding, and demonstrate strong independence. There are days when everything feels too much.

"Haysss kastress, deadline na..." It's 2 AM, and the only thing keeping us awake is the blinking cursor on our screen, the ticking timer, panic, and heartbeat in our chest. Tabs are open, notes are dispersed, and our mind keeps jumping from one requirement to another. We try to type, delete, then type again. Nakakapagod. The pressure is real. But somehow, we're still here, still trying, still pushing because in the third year, stopping is not an option. Even deadlines overlap, research papers demand your time, reports require your confidence, and group works test your patience. Group works? Yes, it becomes its own kind of challenge. Why? May grupo kaseng..... asa na, asan na? "Groupmates, paramdam naman." A simple message, but it carries deep emotional meaning, frustration, stress, and pressure. It is a quiet burden of doing more than your share.

Yet, beyond these struggles, there is something deeper happening, which is growing ourselves. We learn that the third year is not just an academic journey; it is a training ground for social literacy.

In the middle of demonstrations, group chats, classroom discussions, and presentations, we learn how to communicate clearly, assert ourselves, and understand others. We learn when to lead and when to listen. We begin to handle students, placed in front of them and recognizing their unspoken emotions, not just as learners but as leaders. And, this is how social literacy starts. It teaches how to navigate relationships, resolve conflicts, and collaborate despite differences.

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At the same time, familiarity grows. The campus no longer feels overwhelming; it feels like a second home or a part of nature. Friendships deepen, and classmates become support systems. Some people make everything complete and comfortable. You can meet people who stay even when things get hard. This makes us one, one heart and one soul. Hardships make our bond stronger, making ourselves a greatest soldier. Some of us even become informal mentors to younger students, realizing that we are no longer just learners - we are also guides. In this space, we begin to understand our role not only for ourselves, but also in a community, shaping not just our academic identity, but also our social one.

But even with these perks, the fights remain. We need to stand with strength and hope. There is the internal battle; the quiet questions that still echo during moments of exhaustion: Am I on the right path? Am I good enough? And the “Kaya ko kaya” before turns to “Kaya ko pa ba?” These doubts don’t disappear; They grow alongside us, because as they said, “it is a part of the journey”. The future that once we dreamed and once distant now feels uncomfortably close. Beyond academics, as expectations grow, responsibilities expand. Some of us juggle sidelines, helping our families while maintaining our studies, even though it was not easy for us, but we need to do it. As the expectations from ourselves and from society it has now become heavier.

Balancing everything feels like walking a tightrope, where one misstep can disrupt everything.

Yet, in this chaos, growth happens. This year is not just all about our challenges and the hindrances in our lives; it is all about growing and improving ourselves.

At this moment, we begin to notice our small victories: we can now speak in front of our fellow students with confidence, submitting all the tasks and requirements thought impossible, and surviving each exhausting week. These moments may seem ordinary, but they reflect something powerful, and that is, we are changing, we are improving. We are becoming more resilient, more patient, and more aware of ourselves and of others.

This is where social literacy deepens even more. We learn empathy by understanding that everyone is fighting their own different battles. We need to become adaptable, adjusting ourselves to different people, expectations, and situations. And most importantly, we learn connection, that success is not just individual but also shared.

“Malayo pa, pero malapit na.”

We are still in the middle of the journey. There are still deadlines to meet, challenges to face, and doubts to overcome. But we are no longer who we were before. Every sleepless night, every struggle, every small win brings us closer to reality - not just to graduation, but to becoming individuals who can think, communicate, and connect with others meaningfully.

Because in the end, the third year is not just about surviving academics. It is about learning how to exist in a world with others, understanding, responding, and growing together. And maybe that’s the real achievement.

Malayo pa. Pero, malapit na.